

ENERGY-INDEPENDENT HEALTH MONITORING THROUGH SMART TEXTILES AND THERMOELECTRIC TECHNOLOGIES

Halime KARAMAN*

*¹Istanbul University Cerrahpaşa, Faculty of Engineering, Department
of Biomedical Engineering, 34320, İstanbul, TURKEY
ORCID Code: 0000-0001-7090-4695

ABSTRACT

The growing demand for ease of use and energy autonomy in wearable health technologies has accelerated the development of textile-based smart systems. In this context, smart textiles integrated with thermoelectric (TE) materials offer continuous and battery-free health monitoring by converting temperature gradients generated by the user into electrical energy. Due to their flexible and comfortable structures, these textile platforms can be seamlessly incorporated into daily wear, enabling long-term and uninterrupted monitoring of biological data.

This study reviews recent advances in smart textile systems with thermoelectric properties. In particular, the integration of Bi_2Te_3 , Sb_2Te_3 , and organic-inorganic hybrid materials into flexible fiber architectures has demonstrated effective energy conversion even under low temperature gradients. Moreover, sewing techniques, coating methods, and multilayer textile designs have been highlighted for their roles in enhancing both mechanical durability and energy production efficiency .

The findings indicate that thermoelectric smart textiles hold significant application potential not only for personal health monitoring but also for areas such as athletic performance analysis, chronic disease management, and remote medical applications. Recent research on the continuous monitoring of biological parameters, such as blood pressure, further emphasizes the expanding possibilities in this field. Thermoelectric smart textile systems are poised to become fundamental components of future personal healthcare technologies and digital health infrastructures.

Keywords: Smart textiles, thermoelectric generators, wearable health technologies, energy-independent systems, flexible sensors

1.INTRODUCTION

Wearable health technologies have established a significant position in modern medicine by enabling continuous monitoring of individuals' physiological data, thereby facilitating transformative advancements in both personal and public healthcare systems. However, many of these systems rely on external batteries to meet their energy demands, leading to limitations such as reduced operational

time, increased size and weight, and diminished user comfort. Therefore, there is a critical need to develop user-friendly solutions that can operate independently of external power sources and generate their own energy[1].

Thermoelectric generators (TEGs) are semiconductor-based systems that stand out for their ability to convert temperature differences into electrical energy. These technologies, especially when leveraging the temperature differences between the human body and its surrounding environment, can provide a continuous—albeit low-level—energy source. Smart textiles are innovative materials capable of responding to environmental stimuli and altering their functions accordingly. These textiles are used in wearable health technologies by integrating various sensors and energy conversion units to enhance energy efficiency and user comfort. Notably, the integration of thermoelectric (TE) materials into textile structures holds promise for addressing the energy requirements of wearable devices by harvesting electrical energy from biological heat sources, such as body heat [2].

In recent years, alongside inorganic thermoelectric materials such as Bi_2Te_3 and Sb_2Te_3 , organic or hybrid structures like PEDOT:PSS have also been explored for use in textile-based systems. The ability of these materials to exhibit high performance even under low-temperature gradients contributes to enhancing the overall efficiency of such systems. Furthermore, the integration of these materials into textile fibers through techniques such as coating, sewing, or electrospinning has improved both mechanical durability and energy efficiency. [3].

Moreover, thermoelectric smart textiles have the potential to be utilized not only in personal health monitoring systems but also in a wide range of applications, including sports performance assessment, chronic disease management, and remote healthcare solutions [4]. Recent studies, particularly those focusing on the continuous monitoring of biological parameters such as body temperature, perspiration, and blood pressure, demonstrate that the range of application scenarios in this field is rapidly diversifying [5].

This study presents forward-looking solutions based on a literature review and previous research on energy-autonomous health monitoring systems enabled by the integration of smart textiles and thermoelectric Technologies[6]. In particular, the integration of different thermoelectric materials with textile structures, their energy generation capacities, mechanical properties, and potential applications in health monitoring are evaluated.

2. THERMOELECTRIC MATERIALS AND PRINCIPLES

Thermoelectric (TE) materials are semiconductor structures capable of directly converting temperature differences into electrical energy. This conversion is fundamentally based on the physical principle known as the Seebeck effect. When a temperature gradient is established between two ends of a

material, it triggers the movement of electrons and creates an electrical potential difference. As a result, energy can be generated without the need for an external power source [7].

The efficiency of thermoelectric materials is typically expressed by a dimensionless parameter known as the figure of merit (ZT). This value is derived from the combination of electrical conductivity (σ), Seebeck coefficient (S), and thermal conductivity (κ), and is defined by the following equation:

$$ZT = (S^2 \cdot \sigma \cdot T) / \kappa$$

Here, T represents the absolute temperature (Kelvin), and a higher ZT value indicates a material's superior energy conversion performance. For practical applications, a $ZT > 1$ is generally considered an acceptable threshold; however, in applications that require flexibility and comfort—such as textiles—criteria such as flexibility, biocompatibility, and mechanical durability are equally critical alongside the ZT value. In recent years, the development of both inorganic (Bi_2Te_3 , Sb_2Te_3) and organic or hybrid thermoelectric materials (e.g., PEDOT:PSS) has gained considerable attention. Bi_2Te_3 is known for its high ZT values at low temperatures, while organic materials such as PEDOT:PSS offer advantages for wearable systems due to their inherent flexibility [8][9]. These materials can generate meaningful energy even under low-temperature gradients, enabling their integration into wearable textiles and establishing them as key components in energy-autonomous health monitoring systems [10].

2.1. Seebeck Effect and Energy Conversion Principle

The Seebeck effect, which forms the foundation of thermoelectric energy conversion, was first described by Thomas Johann Seebeck in 1821. This effect is based on the principle that when a temperature difference is established between the two ends of a semiconductor material, an electrical voltage is generated across the material. The carriers (electrons or holes) at the hot end possess higher energy and tend to move toward the cold end, leading to the formation of a potential difference—i.e., a voltage—within the system [11].

This phenomenon is quantitatively expressed by the Seebeck coefficient (S). The Seebeck coefficient is defined as the ratio of the generated voltage (V) to the applied temperature difference (ΔT) and is typically measured in units of $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ (microvolts per Kelvin).

$$S = \Delta V / \Delta T$$

Figure 1. Seebeck effect: A temperature gradient across the material generates a voltage (ΔV), driving charge carriers from the hot side to the cold side.

The Seebeck coefficient varies depending on the type of material and the temperature range. A good thermoelectric material should possess a high Seebeck coefficient and electrical conductivity, along with low thermal conductivity. The balanced combination of these three parameters determines the material's energy conversion efficiency [12].

In wearable systems, unlike conventional thermoelectric generators, materials must operate with low-temperature gradient sources such as the human body. Therefore, material selection and structural design become more critical. In this context, there is an increasing demand for thermoelectric materials that are flexible, lightweight, and capable of efficient performance when in contact with the body.

2.2. Biocompatible and Flexible Thermoelectric Materials: Performance Criteria and Properties

The success of thermoelectric materials in wearable health technologies depends not only on energy conversion efficiency but also on their flexibility, biocompatibility, and long-term safety for use. Inorganic materials such as Bi_2Te_3 and Sb_2Te_3 stand out for their high ZT values at low temperatures [8]. However, the rigid nature of such materials imposes limitations in wearable applications. Thermoelectric performance is primarily expressed by the ZT value (figure of merit), which is defined by the interaction of parameters such as the Seebeck coefficient (S), electrical conductivity (σ), absolute temperature (T), and thermal conductivity (κ):

$$ZT = (S^2 \cdot \sigma \cdot T) / \kappa$$

A high ZT value ($ZT > 1$) is ideal for thermoelectric efficiency; however, the rigid nature of inorganic materials such as Bi_2Te_3 and Sb_2Te_3 limits their use in wearable applications [13]. Therefore, organic conductive polymers such as PEDOT:PSS have gained prominence in recent years. These materials offer ease of integration into textile-based systems due to their flexible and lightweight structures, and they exhibit biocompatible properties, making them suitable for applications in contact with the human body [3]. Moreover, biocompatibility is a critical criterion for ensuring user safety, particularly in applications involving prolonged skin contact. Organic-inorganic hybrid structures, which combine the advantages of both material groups, show great promise in this field by offering both high thermoelectric performance and mechanical compatibility. Hybrid systems that integrate PEDOT:PSS

with Bi_2Te_3 have demonstrated the ability to generate meaningful energy even under low-temperature gradients. [14].

Table 1. Comparison of ZT Values, Flexibility, and Biocompatibility of Thermoelectric Materials

Material	ZT Value (~300K)	Flexibility	Biocompatibility	Reference
Bi_2Te_3	1.0–1.5	Low	Low	[8]
Sb_2Te_3	0.8–1.2	Low	Low	[8]
PEDOT:PSS	0.1–0.42	High	High	[13][15]
Bi_2Te_3 /PEDOT:PSS Hybrid	0.6–1.0	Moderate	Moderate	[16]
Rigid Bi_2Te_3 , Sb_2Te_3	1.1–1.9	Very Low	Very Low	[9]

3. THERMOELECTRIC APPLICATIONS IN SMART TEXTILES

The integration of thermoelectric materials into textile surfaces is one of the key factors determining the performance of wearable systems. The success of this integration must address not only energy conversion efficiency but also parameters such as flexibility, breathability, washability, and user comfort. Currently, three main techniques are commonly used for this purpose: coating, sewing/embroidery, and electrospinning.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of thermoelectric material integration techniques

3.1. Coating

The coating method involves the application of thermoelectric active materials (such as PEDOT:PSS, Bi₂Te₃ nanoparticles, or composite solutions) onto textile substrates using various techniques. These techniques include production-compatible methods such as spray coating, dip-coating, roll-to-roll printing, and inkjet printing. The ability of conductive polymers like PEDOT:PSS to be applied in water-based solutions makes this method particularly sustainable.

Thermoelectric films produced by coating are typically a few microns thick and can adapt to the movements of textiles thanks to their flexible nature. However, parameters such as coating thickness, surface uniformity, and material–textile interaction directly impact energy efficiency. In particular, surface modifications may be required when coating hydrophobic fabrics [15].

3.2. Embroidering

This method involves the direct incorporation of pre-treated, thermoelectric conductive threads (such as carbon nanotube-reinforced polymer fibers, metal-coated fibers, or fibers impregnated with PEDOT:PSS) into the textile structure. The embroidery technique allows the physical placement of threads within the fabric, which enhances the mechanical durability of the conductive paths and preserves the structural integrity of wireless wearable systems [16].

This approach is preferred in applications such as medical textiles and athlete monitoring. However, as the needle passes through the fabric during the embroidery process, it may weaken the textile structure. Therefore, optimizing the stitching geometry and selecting threads that are resistant to deformation are critical considerations [17].

3.3. Electrospinning

Electrospinning enables the production of nanoscale fibers from a solution under high voltage, allowing their direct deposition onto textile substrates. Thermoelectric fibers produced using this method can maximize the benefit from temperature differences due to their high surface area. In particular, solutions containing PEDOT:PSS, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), and carbon nanotubes are commonly used in this process [18]. Electrospun structures adhere strongly to textiles, minimizing thermal interfaces and optimizing energy generation even under low gradients such as body temperature. However, the process requires complex equipment, and material selection is quite limited.

Table 2. Performance and Integration Characteristics of Thermoelectric Materials in Wearable Systems

Method	Description	Advantages	Limitations	Energy Capacity	Generation	References
Coating	Application of thermoelectric materials such as PEDOT:PSS or Bi ₂ Te ₃ onto fabric surfaces via spray, dip-coating, or inkjet printing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low-cost - Easily integrable into production - Provides flexible and lightweight structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low-cost - Easily integrable into production - Provides flexible and lightweight structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PEDOT:PSS-coated textiles can generate 4.3 mV at a 75.2 K temperature difference [19] - PEDOT:PSS/Bi₂Te₃/rGO composites can generate 1.2 μW at a 65 K temperature difference [3] 		[15],[18]
Embroidering	Direct stitching of thermoelectric conductive threads (e.g., PEDOT:PSS-coated threads) into fabric structures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High mechanical durability - Suitable for flexible systems - Preferred for medical textile applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not suitable for mass production - Risk of deformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Embroidered textiles with 38 thermoelectric elements can generate 143 mV at a 116°C temperature difference [20] - Thermoelectric fabrics with 8 p-n couples can generate 10 mV and 8 nW at a 25 K temperature difference [21] 		[20],[22]
Electrospinning	Application of nanoscale thermoelectric fibers onto textile substrates via electrospinning.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides high surface area - Creates a flexible and lightweight structure - Enables energy generation even at low-temperature gradients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires complex setup - Material selection may be limited 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PEDOT:PSS nanofibers can deliver a power density of 70 mW/m² at a 44 K temperature difference [5]. - Te-PEDOT:PSS composites can generate 26 nW/cm² at a 15 K temperature difference [23] 		[24],[23]

3.2. Material–Mechanical Compatibility

In wearable thermoelectric systems, the mechanical compatibility between the material and the textile substrate plays a critical role in device performance and user comfort. This compatibility is defined by the material's ability to maintain its conductivity and structural integrity under mechanical deformations such as bending, stretching, and twisting.

PEDOT:PSS has been widely used in wearable thermoelectric applications due to its flexibility and conductivity [25]. However, the mechanical durability of pure PEDOT:PSS can be limited. Therefore, various strategies have been developed to enhance the mechanical properties of PEDOT:PSS. For example, forming composites of PEDOT:PSS with flexible polymers such as polyurethane (PU) can improve both flexibility and durability [26]. Additionally, the combination of PEDOT:PSS with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) can enhance both electrical and mechanical performance [26].

Carbon nanotubes, particularly single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs), not only support thermoelectric performance with their high tensile strength (>100 GPa) and conductivity ($\sim 10^6$ S/m), but also improve the material's flexibility and mechanical robustness. PEDOT:PSS/CNT composites have demonstrated the ability to retain their electrical properties over 1000 cycles of bending tests [24].

Finally, hybrid polymer structures that combine these materials can integrate various requirements such as electrical performance, flexibility, and durability into a single system. For example, PEDOT:PSS/CNT/PU ternary structures provide meaningful energy generation under a 50 K temperature gradient while exhibiting superior resistance to bending and stretching conditions [23].

3.3. Energy Generation Capacity and Durability

The practical use of thermoelectric textiles depends on their ability to generate a meaningful level of electrical energy under low temperature gradients (typically <10 K). Recent studies have indicated that power densities ranging from 20–100 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$, harvested from the temperature difference between the human body and the surrounding environment, may be sufficient to operate low-power biosensors [27].

In addition, it is expected that thermoelectric performance remains stable over long-term use, and that the textile retains its physical properties. Therefore, durability tests—such as bending cycles, humidity/temperature cycling, and others—are essential for demonstrating the reliability of the system.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of thermoelectric material integration with textile substrates, highlighting energy generation capacity, mechanical compatibility, and durability in wearable applications

4. HEALTH MONITORING APPLICATIONS

Thermoelectric smart textiles enable the continuous, wireless, and energy-autonomous monitoring of various biological parameters by converting temperature differences generated from the user's body into electrical energy. These systems not only meet the energy demands of wearable sensor platforms but also provide the foundation for long-term health monitoring solutions.

4.1. Body Temperature, Heart Rate, and Sweat Analysis

Wearable sensors powered by thermoelectric systems are primarily used for monitoring essential biophysiological parameters such as body temperature, heart rate, and sweat composition. The continuous tracking of these parameters enables early detection of critical conditions, from febrile illnesses to cardiovascular anomalies. In this context, temperature sensors integrated with PEDOT:PSS-based thermoelectric textiles are capable of generating usable energy even under low-temperature gradients (<10 K)

[28]. Electrospun sensors reinforced with CNTs are capable of both self-powering via thermoelectric mechanisms and responding to sweat pH and ion composition [29].

4.2. Athlete Performance Monitoring and Chronic Disease Management

Wearable sensors powered by thermoelectric systems can be utilized for performance analysis in athletes or as continuous monitoring systems in patients with chronic conditions. Information on body temperature and sweat composition during exercise is valuable for assessing hydration, electrolyte balance, and metabolic responses.

Smart textile-based sweat sensors detect ions (Na^+ , K^+), pH, and hydration levels in sweat through electrochemical or thermoelectric components integrated into the fabric surface. These data are processed by low-power circuits and wirelessly transmitted to mobile devices, enabling real-time assessment for athlete performance monitoring

[30]. In chronic diseases such as heart failure and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), continuous monitoring of body temperature and movement enables the remote tracking of symptomatic changes[31].

4.3. Remote Health Monitoring Solutions

Health monitoring systems integrated with wearable thermoelectric generators can operate continuously and without batteries by converting human body heat into a constant energy source. These systems are particularly valuable in remote field applications—such as rural areas, disaster zones, and military operations—where access to infrastructure is limited.

They enable uninterrupted physiological data monitoring (e.g., body temperature, heart rate, movement) for up to 72 hours and can supply power levels of approximately 20–100 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$, sufficient to continuously power low-energy sensors such as temperature, ECG, or accelerometers. This allows the system to transmit data to mobile applications and function as an early warning system in critical situations [32]

Table 3. Performance and Integration Characteristics of Thermoelectric Materials in Wearable Systems

Device / Material	Type	Power Output	Temperature Gradient	Target Application	Material Flexibility / Integration	Manufacturing Method / Integration
PEDOT:PSS/Bi ₂ Te ₃ /rGO composite	TE composite	400–600 μW	65 K	Wearable low-power sensors	High (flexible, wearable)	Coating (spray, dip-coating)
3D flexible TE fabric	TE fabric	20–100 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$	-	Wearable energy harvesting	High (textile-based, wearable)	Fiber-based textile weaving/integration
Flexible TE films	TE film	70 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$	44 K	Biosignal monitoring (pulse, temperature)	Medium (film-based, textile-compatible)	PEDOT:PSS solution casting
PEDOT:PSS aerogels	TE aerogel	26 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$	-	Nanosensor powering	Medium (fragile, aerogel structure)	3D printing and inkjet printing
TE-based pressure	TE sensor	4.3 mV	75.2 K	Temperature	High	Multilayer thin film

sensor				sensing via (textile-thermal gradient compatible)		
Flexible generator	TE generator	18.4 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$	~ 33 K	Sports/field health applications	High (flexible elastomer structure)	Embedded elastomer structure TE
Wet-spun fiber	PEDOT:PSS TE fiber	~ 200 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ (Seebeck)	-	Temperature sensing fibers	High (fiber-based)	Wet spinning (electrospinning)

4. DISCUSSION: ENERGY GENERATION POTENTIAL, GAPS IN THE LITERATURE, AND IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES

Thermoelectric (TE) wearable systems are gaining increasing significance in energy-autonomous health monitoring technologies. Numerous sensors and devices developed in recent years demonstrate the potential to generate sufficient energy for low-power applications, potentially eliminating the need for batteries. For instance, PEDOT:PSS/Bi₂Te₃/rGO composites can generate approximately 1.2 μW under a 65 K temperature difference, and this value can reach 400–600 μW as the surface area is increased [3]. Studies on three-dimensional flexible thermoelectric fabrics have demonstrated the ability to continuously generate energy in the range of 20–100 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$, effectively powering low-power biosensors [33].

However, there are still significant gaps in the literature. Many studies report power generation under specific temperature differences, yet they do not assess the long-term compatibility of these outputs with actual sensor systems. For instance, in the TE-based pressure sensor developed by Wang et al., a voltage output of 4.3 mV was achieved under a 75.2 K temperature gradient; however, application scenarios for how this output could be utilized in medical monitoring systems remain limited.

[28]. Similarly, structures such as PEDOT:PSS aerogels, which meet the power requirements at the nanosensor level [23], show potential but have not been sufficiently analyzed in terms of physical durability and long-term stability. In this study, a voltage output of approximately 1.2 mV was achieved under a 65 K temperature difference; while this output indicates that low-power sensor modules could be utilized for tasks such as short-range data communication, the long-term stability of the system under sustained load still requires further testing [34].

Another key area of discussion is the material development process and production scalability. While many materials have demonstrated success at the laboratory scale, they often suffer from performance

losses during the transition to industrial textile manufacturing lines—particularly in terms of structural integrity, coating uniformity, and flexibility. Nanoscale structures produced through methods such as electrospinning or 3D printing present challenges in terms of repeatability and standardization[23],[30].

This remains a key factor limiting the integration of thermoelectric textile technologies into large-scale healthcare systems.

In addition, user safety, biocompatibility, and regulatory considerations are addressed in only a limited number of studies. The long-term skin contact of flexible electronic materials—especially metal-doped systems such as Bi₂Te₃ and Sb₂Te₃—may pose potential toxicological risks. While there is a growing trend toward selecting biocompatible alternatives, such as PEDOT:PSS, to ensure material safety, it is evident that clinical evaluation and approval processes have not yet been initiated for most of the devices developed to date [4], [13]. The number of wearable thermoelectric devices evaluated under medical device regulations such as CE or FDA is extremely limited.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The need for energy autonomy in wearable health technologies has brought thermoelectric smart textile systems into focus. Studies conducted over the past decade have demonstrated that with the development of materials capable of generating energy even at low temperature gradients, human body heat can be effectively utilized as a power source [3], [4], [24]. Systems based on PEDOT:PSS, Bi₂Te₃, and organic-inorganic hybrid structures are particularly suitable for powering low-power sensors, typically generating power levels below 100 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ [23], [28].

However, most of these systems remain at the laboratory scale and face numerous barriers to clinical or industrial translation. Only a limited number of studies in the literature provide information on the long-term durability of the developed thermoelectric systems, their biocompatibility after skin contact, and their compatibility with standard healthcare applications [4], [12].

Finally, an emerging approach that has not been sufficiently explored in the literature but holds the potential to revolutionize future wearable technologies is the concept of adaptive thermoelectric (TE) systems. In these systems, multiple thermoelectric modules with different ZT values and physical configurations are integrated into a single platform. Temperature gradients across the human body are analyzed through microcontroller-assisted thermal mapping, allowing the system to dynamically redirect energy harvesting to the most efficient module at any given moment.

For example, if a low temperature gradient is detected in the neck region, the device can automatically switch to a module located in the arm, where a higher gradient exists. This configuration maximizes energy efficiency while enabling real-time adaptation to physiological and environmental conditions. Additionally, optimizing such systems based on user-specific thermal profiles has the potential to

create a new paradigm for personalized health technologies. These adaptive systems could provide significant advantages in scenarios where energy demands fluctuate, such as chronic disease management, sleep monitoring, or post-exercise metabolic response tracking.

In this context, the following strategic recommendations are critical for advancing the field: Future research should focus not only on energy generation but also on the development of **smart system** architectures that integrate sensing, decision-making, and energy routing components.

In conclusion, thermoelectric-based smart textile systems hold significant potential for transforming wearable health technologies. To ensure their sustainable integration into clinical applications, a holistic roadmap that brings together interdisciplinary collaborations—including materials science, device engineering, data analysis, and health sciences—is essential.

Moreover, these systems have the potential to create societal benefits beyond healthcare, including applications in disaster management, military operations, and elderly care, particularly in scenarios where energy access is limited.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. I. Lai, C. F. Lee, and F. J. Wei, “Smart clothing as a noninvasive method to measure the physiological cardiac parameters,” *Healthc.*, vol. 9, no. 10, p. 1318, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3390/HEALTHCARE9101318/S1.
- [2] G. Chen, X. Xiao, X. Zhao, T. Tat, M. Bick, and J. Chen, “Electronic Textiles for Wearable Point-of-Care Systems,” *Chem. Rev.*, vol. 122, no. 3, pp. 3259–3291, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1021/ACS.CHEMREV.1C00502.
- [3] V. Rathi, K. Singh, K. P. S. Parmar, R. K. Brajpuriya, and A. Kumar, “Improved thermoelectric performance of PEDOT:PSS/Bi₂Te₃/reduced graphene oxide ternary composite films for energy harvesting applications,” *RSC Adv.*, vol. 14, no. 47, pp. 34883–34892, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1039/D4RA06184E.
- [4] S. Hong, T. Yu, Z. Wang, and C. H. Lee, “Biomaterials for reliable wearable health monitoring: Applications in skin and eye integration,” *Biomaterials*, vol. 314, p. 122862, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOMATERIALS.2024.122862.
- [5] F. C. Huang, X. Di Sun, Y. Shi, and L. J. Pan, “Textile electronics for ubiquitous health monitoring,” *Soft Sci 2024;440.*, vol. 4, no. 4, p. N/A-N/A, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.20517/SS.2024.37.
- [6] “Smart Textiles: A New Era of Wearable Technology - The Brighter Side of News.” <https://www.thebrighterside.news/post/smart-textiles-a-new-era-of-wearable-technology/> (accessed May 23, 2025).
- [7] I. M. Abdel-Motaleb and S. M. Qadri, “Thermoelectric Devices: Principles and Future Trends.”
- [8] T. Q. Kimberly, K. M. Ciesielski, X. Qi, E. S. Toberer, and S. M. Kauzlarich, “High Thermoelectric Performance in 2D Sb₂Te₃ and Bi₂Te₃ Nanoplate Composites Enabled by Energy Carrier Filtering and Low Thermal Conductivity,” *ACS Appl. Electron. Mater.*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 2816–2825, May 2024, doi: 10.1021/ACSAELM.3C00385/SUPPL_FILE/EL3C00385_SI_001.PDF.
- [9] R. Wang, R. Sun, Y. Ren, Y. Ma, and L. Ma, “Preparation of high-performance Ag₂Se NWs/PEDOT:PSS composite films and influence of PEDOT:PSS content on thermoelectric properties,” *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Eng.*, vol. 20, no. 1, Dec. 2025, doi: 10.1186/S40712-025-00235-6.
- [10] X. He *et al.*, “Three-dimensional flexible thermoelectric fabrics for smart wearables,” *Nat. Commun.* 2025 161, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Mar. 2025, doi: 10.1038/s41467-025-57889-1.

- [11] G. J. Snyder and E. S. Toberer, "Complex thermoelectric materials," *Nat. Mater.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 105–114, Feb. 2008, doi: 10.1038/NMAT2090.
- [12] E. H. Hwang, E. Rossi, and S. Das Sarma, "Theory of thermopower in two-dimensional graphene," *Phys. Rev. B*, vol. 80, no. 23, p. 235415, Dec. 2009, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevB.80.235415.
- [13] Y. Zhang and S. J. Park, "Flexible organic thermoelectric materials and devices for wearable green energy harvesting," *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 11, no. 5, May 2019, doi: 10.3390/POLYM11050909.
- [14] Y. Li, H. Hu, T. Salim, G. Cheng, Y. M. Lam, and J. Ding, "Flexible Wet-Spun PEDOT:PSS Microfibers Integrating Thermal-Sensing and Joule Heating Functions for Smart Textiles," *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 15, no. 16, p. 3432, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.3390/POLYM15163432/S1.
- [15] G. B. Tseghai, B. Malengier, K. A. Fante, A. B. Nigusse, and L. Van Langenhove, "Integration of Conductive Materials with Textile Structures, an Overview," *Sensors 2020, Vol. 20, Page 6910*, vol. 20, no. 23, p. 6910, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.3390/S20236910.
- [16] O. Pamuk *et al.*, "Elektronik Devrelerin Nakış İşlemi ile Kumaş Yüzeylerine Uygulanması," *DEÜ FMD*, vol. 23, no. 67, pp. 319–325, 2021, doi: 10.21205/deufmd.2021236728.
- [17] A. Lund, Y. Tian, S. Darabi, and C. Müller, "A polymer-based textile thermoelectric generator for wearable energy harvesting," *J. Power Sources*, vol. 480, p. 228836, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2020.228836.
- [18] N. Liu, G. Fang, J. Wan, H. Zhou, H. Long, and X. Zhao, "Electrospun PEDOT:PSS–PVA nanofiber based ultrahigh-strain sensors with controllable electrical conductivity," *J. Mater. Chem.*, vol. 21, no. 47, pp. 18962–18966, Nov. 2011, doi: 10.1039/C1JM14491J.
- [19] Y. Du *et al.*, "Thermoelectric fabrics: Toward power generating clothing," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–6, Mar. 2015, doi: 10.1038/SREP06411;TECHMETA=128;SUBJMETA=1028,2736,299,301,639,923;KWRD=POLYMERS,THERMOELECTRICS.
- [20] J. D. Ryan *et al.*, "All-Organic Textile Thermoelectrics with Carbon-Nanotube-Coated n-Type Yarns," *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 2934–2941, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1021/ACSAEM.8B00617.
- [21] L. Wang and K. Zhang, "Textile-Based Thermoelectric Generators and Their Applications," *Energy Environ. Mater.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 67–79, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1002/EEM2.12045.
- [22] A. C. Sparavigna, L. Florio, J. Avloni, and A. Henn, "Polypyrrole Coated PET Fabrics for Thermal Applications," *Mater. Sci. Appl.*, vol. 01, no. 04, pp. 253–259, 2010, doi: 10.4236/MSA.2010.14037.
- [23] H. E. Baysal *et al.*, "Omnidirectional 3D Printing of PEDOT: PSS Aerogels with Tunable Electromechanical Performance: A Playground for Unconventional Stretchable Interconnects and Thermoelectrics," *Adv. Sci.*, vol. 12, no. 11, p. 2412491, Mar. 2025, doi: 10.1002/ADVS.202412491;WGROU:STRING:PUBLICATION.
- [24] X. Li, K. Cai, M. Gao, Y. Du, and S. Shen, "Recent advances in flexible thermoelectric films and devices," *Nano Energy*, vol. 89, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.NANOEN.2021.106309.
- [25] G. B. Tseghai, D. A. Mengistie, B. Malengier, K. A. Fante, and L. Van Langenhove, "PEDOT:PSS-based conductive textiles and their applications," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 20, no. 7, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.3390/S20071881.
- [26] J. Kim *et al.*, "Self-healing, stretchable and recyclable polyurethane-PEDOT:PSS conductive blends," *Mater. Horizons*, vol. 11, no. 15, pp. 3548–3560, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1039/D4MH00203B.
- [27] X. Li, K. Cai, M. Gao, Y. Du, and S. Shen, "Recent advances in flexible thermoelectric films and devices," *Nano Energy*, vol. 89, p. 106309, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.NANOEN.2021.106309.
- [28] Y. Wang *et al.*, "Self-powered wearable pressure sensing system for continuous healthcare monitoring enabled by flexible thin-film thermoelectric generator," *Nano Energy*, vol. 73, p. 104773, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.NANOEN.2020.104773.
- [29] Y. Zhang, H. Wang, H. Lu, S. Li, and Y. Zhang, "Electronic fibers and textiles: Recent progress and perspective," *iScience*, vol. 24, no. 7, p. 102716, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.ISCI.2021.102716.

- [30] A. Akter, M. M. H. Apu, Y. R. Veeranki, T. N. Baroud, and H. F. Posada-Quintero, "Recent Studies on Smart Textile-Based Wearable Sweat Sensors for Medical Monitoring: A Systematic Review," *J. Sens. Actuator Networks*, vol. 13, no. 4, Aug. 2024, doi: 10.3390/JSAN13040040.
- [31] S. Li *et al.*, "Advanced Textile-Based Wearable Biosensors for Healthcare Monitoring," *Biosens. 2023, Vol. 13, Page 909*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. 909, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.3390/BIOS13100909.
- [32] M. Zadan *et al.*, "Stretchable Thermoelectric Generators for Self-Powered Wearable Health Monitoring," *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, vol. 34, no. 39, p. 2404861, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1002/ADFM.202404861;REQUESTEDJOURNAL:JOURNAL:16163028;WGROU:STRING:PUBLICATION.
- [33] X. He *et al.*, "Three-dimensional flexible thermoelectric fabrics for smart wearables," *Nat. Commun. 2025 161*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Mar. 2025, doi: 10.1038/s41467-025-57889-1.
- [34] K. Gürkan, H. Karaman, and S. Ballikaya, "Optimization of high-performance flexible thermoelectric generator from material synthesis to simulation and device application," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 291, p. 117335, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2023.117335.